

Sustainable coastal groundwater management and pollution reduction through innovative governance in a changing climate

Sustain-COAST (PRIMA 2018 - Section 2 / Research & Innovation Activities (RIA))

Sustain-COAST

REDUCE · RECYCLE · REUSE · RECOVER

Deliverable 2.2b: Report on the application of HRMA for the 4 monitored sites

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¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium, **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

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Deliverable abstract

Sustain-COAST “Sustainable coastal groundwater management and pollution reduction through innovative governance in a changing climate” is an R&I project co-funded under the PRIMA 2018 programme Section II, for a period of three years starting from June 2019. The Sustain-COAST consortium is led by the Technical University of Crete (TUC) and comprises a multidisciplinary team of seven partners from six countries. Sustain-COAST intends to develop a calibrated multi-criteria decision supporting system (DSS) and a web Geographical Information System output accessible for water stakeholders and policymakers.

Task 2.2b (D2.2b) aims to improve groundwater monitoring in the four case studies. The Turkish and Italian case studies are historically well monitored using intensive grab sampling in different observation wells, so it has been decided by the consortium partners from the beginning of the project that additional monitoring using high-resolution monitoring approach (HRMA) is not needed. However, the Greek and Tunisian case studies have shown a clear need for further monitoring as the traditional monitoring strategies were limited to detecting the continuous changes in groundwater levels and rapid deterioration of water quality due to complex and interconnected anthropogenic and climate-related changes in the region. Thus, as detailed below, the Greek and Tunisian case studies have benefited from implementing high-resolution sensors during the project period. It is well known that a good evaluation of groundwater dynamics and surface water quality depends on the number of assessed parameters, sampling frequencies, and spatial distribution. Low-resolution and irregular (limited in time) grab sampling could not capture fine dynamics of water quantity and quality status, resulting in significant uncertainties in the groundwater functioning. The recent development of high-frequency sensors has enabled the monitoring of solute concentrations at sub-hourly time scales, which are relevant for processes understanding and evaluating management practices. The Greek and Tunisian case studies have used an innovative monitoring scheme for water resources accounting and quality control that compliment the historically grab-sampling (biweekly) data with the strengths of high-resolution monitoring approach (HRMA) (very tight measures: lower than one hour) for knowledge production needed for sustainable decision-making. A combination of grab-sampling and HRMA has been shown to enhance groundwater monitoring and assessment under rapidly changing conditions and guide efficient management. The HRMA consists of implementing multiple optical sensors at real sites to assess specific parameters of interest regarding spatial and temporal dynamics. This analysis was prioritized in hotspot locations of each case study depending on the specificity of each site and the suggestion of stakeholders.

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1. SUSTAIN-COAST PROJECT OVERVIEW

The need for the implementation of innovative governance of coastal aquifers, considering the technological development and socio-economic factors, has become a worldwide necessity. In compliance with the challenges and scope of the PRIMA call topic 1.1.2 “Sustainable, integrated water management”, Sustain-COAST was designed to explore innovative governance approaches of coastal aquifers among multiple water users and beneficiaries, under the uncertainties posed by the changing climate conditions, in four Mediterranean countries (Greece, Italy, Tunisia and Turkey).

Sustain-COAST “Sustainable coastal groundwater management and pollution reduction through innovative governance in a changing climate” is an R&I project co-funded under the PRIMA 2018 programme, Section II, for three years starting from June 2019. Sustain-COAST consortium is led by the Technical University of Crete (TUC) and is composed of a multidisciplinary team of seven partners from six countries.

Sustain-COAST intends to develop a calibrated multi-criteria decision supporting system (DSS) and a web Geographical Information System output accessible for water stakeholders and policymakers. The DSS and the output, combined with a specific projection activity, social actors in a learning process around water issues at catchment scale based on visualization of interactive thematic maps, ii) the use of advanced technologies and tools, such as optical sensors and remote sensing capacities for participatory monitoring of water, iii) the use of calibrated numerical models for the time-space simulation of water quantity and quality progress.

Sustain-COAST will explore new governance approaches to effectively support the coastal aquifer conservation against anthropogenic and climatic pressures by promoting innovative water management concepts based on the 4R principles: Reduce, Recycle, Reuse and Recover.

Thanks to Sustain-COAST, new options will be available to private and public bodies for sustainable Mediterranean coastal groundwater management based on an improved response-ability of all concerned actors taking into account the local environmental and socio-economic context.

2. DOCUMENT OBJECTIVES

This deliverable presents the results of implementing the High-Resolution Monitoring Approach (HRMA) strategy for the Greek and Tunisian case studies throughout the project period. This deliverable illustrates the importance of HRMA, especially in areas experiencing rapid changes where when the traditional monitoring strategies are failed to offer insightful knowledge that can guide effective groundwater management. The Greek case studies focuses on the continuity of groundwater

monitoring using different parameters as proxies for groundwater sources and mixing during the declining and recovering phases. However, the HRMA strategy used in the Tunisian case study aimed to identify the surface water-groundwater hotspots and their interacting processes. The two HRMA monitoring strategies implemented in the Greek and Tunisian case studies can serve as two typical examples of implementing the same approaches in other demo sites experiencing the same features.

3. The HRMA implemented in Malia area in Greece

For groundwater analysis in the Malia area of Crete, Greece, the focus was on hydrological and geochemical assessments to evaluate the quality and characteristics of the groundwater. Techniques commonly used for groundwater monitoring include:

1. Groundwater Sampling: Collection of groundwater samples from wells, boreholes, or springs in the study area.
2. Instrument monitoring: pH, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids (TDS), major ions (e.g., chloride, sulfate, nitrate), groundwater level

In the Malia study area, two sensors (In Situ AquaTroll200, with data logger) have been installed since October 2021. Each sensor measures in hourly time step the following parameters:

- Pressure
- Temperature
- Depth
- Actual conductivity
- Specific conductivity
- Salinity
- Total Dissolved Solids
- Resistivity
- Density of water

The collected (hourly) data are sent every three hours to the server of the GeoEnvironmental Laboratory in .txt format (Figure 1). For the first sensor (Depth: 130m), there are 13612 records from 30/10/2021 until the present time, and for the second sensor (Depth: 90m) 11746 records from 12/1/2022 until the present time.

```

Attempt 01
Site:
Device: T3S1-3E-V-1T
S/n: 18033675
19-May-2023 13:00:12
Sensor n. 01 Type: AquaTR200[5] s/n:763370 Batt:76%
Record n,Date,Time,Sensor n,Pressure(mBar)[2:21],Temperature(°C)[1:1],Depth(m)[3:35],Actual Conduct.(uS/cm)[9:65],
Specific Conduct.(uS/cm)[10:65],Salinity(PSU)[12:97],Tot Diss. Solids(ppt)[13:114],Resistivity(ohm*cm)[11:81],Density of Water(g/cm3)[14:129]
13613,19/05/2023,11:00,01,292.86,17.24,2.99,1508.22,1770.81,0.91,1.15,663.04,1.00
13614,19/05/2023,12:00,01,292.44,17.24,2.98,1509.03,1771.76,0.91,1.15,662.68,1.00
13615,19/05/2023,13:00,01,292.77,17.24,2.99,1509.14,1771.91,0.91,1.15,662.63,1.00
----- STATUS -----
- Signal (GSM): 90%
- Temperature: 28.50 °C
- Battery Level: 12.54 V
- Solar Panel Current: 8.94 mA
- Solar Panel Current Peak of today= 8.94 mA
- Firmware version: 13.26
- System Resets: 6
----- SETTINGS -----
MODEM PARAMETERS:
- Access Point Name: internet
- Sntp Server: smtp.tre.it
- To Address:
- To CC Address:
- Ftp Server: 147.27.33.189
- File Name: 18033675.txt
- Phone Number for SMS alarms:
- Second Phone Number for SMS alarms:
LOGGING PARAMETERS:
- Logging period(hh:mm): 01:00
- Save data every: 08 readings
- Send data every: 3 saved data
PROBES:
- 01 Type: AquaTR200 Addr: 1
----- End of Message -----

```

Figure 1. Sensor measurements highlight

Figure 2. Geographical location of the Greek case study (Site 1).

Figure 3. An overview of the location and power connection of the HRMA of Greek Site 1.

Figure 4. Raw data as shown in the data logger from the Greek Site 1.

Figure 5. Geographical location of the Greek case study (Site 2).

Figure 6. An overview in the second observation well for the Greek case study (Site 2).

Figure 7. Raw data as shown in the data logger for the Greek case study (Site 2).

4. The HRMA implemented in Wadi El Bey area in Tunisia

The Wadi El Bey watershed is the most polluted area in Tunisia due to significant anthropogenic pressure due to agricultural practices and inadequate treatment of urban and industrial wastewater.

While data on the evolution of surface water resources and groundwater levels are regularly and effectively gathered, there is a lack of a comprehensive spatial distribution, an adequate number of parameters assessed, and an appropriate sampling frequency for monitoring water quality.

In the context of the Sustain-COAST project, an innovative monitoring system that combines conventional sampling methods with high-frequency sampling techniques employing high-resolution monitoring sensors (HRMS) has been implemented in sampled locations in Wadi El Bey to quantify the concentration of nitrates and monitor and assess the water quality.

The implemented HRMA sensors have the following characteristics:

Acquired HRMA: **Aqua TROLL 600** unit with a Bluetooth transmission unit and operating software.

Table 1. Characteristics of Aqua TROLL 600 unit with a Bluetooth transmission unit and operating software.

Trade mark	In-Situ
Model	AquaTroll 600
Type	Multiparameter sonde
Sensors	Temperature, N-NO ³⁻
Price	≈ 4850 EUR

Sensor	Accuracy	Range	Resolution
Temperature	± 0.1° C	5 to 50° C	0.01° C
Nitrate	±2 mg/L	0 to 40,000 mg/L as N	0.01 mg/L

The AquaTroll 600, supplied by In-situ Company, is employed for real-time measurement and monitoring of nitrate concentration in the wadi as a key aspect of research studies within the project.

The results obtained from the sampling campaigns using HRMA were compared to those obtained with IC (Ion chromatography). Unfortunately, the values provided by HRMA are significantly higher than those obtained using the ion chromatography technique, which makes the comparison impossible (see the maps below given in Figures 8 and 9).

There are two reasons for the observed differences between the results of the nitrate concentration measurements made at sample locations using the IC method and the HRMA methodology:

- 1- The filtration and dilution processes that may occur before IC analysis can induce measurement errors and some degree of imprecision.
- 2- The excessive pollution of the surface waters can impact the sensors and cause values that occasionally surpass the device's measurement range. This, in turn, leads to errors in the measurements taken at other points.

Figure 8. Spatial locations of sampling points for surface water and groundwater quality monitoring and their corresponding Nitrate concentrations for the Tunisian case study during the first monitoring campaign.

Figure 9. Spatial locations of sampling points for surface water and groundwater quality monitoring and their corresponding Nitrate concentrations for the Tunisian case study during the monitoring second campaign.

The severe pollution state of the wadis in the watershed of Wadi El Bey, the security limitations that make it impossible to continuously implement the in-situ sensor, the high cost of the sensors, their high sensitivity, and the issues related to their maintenance and calibration prevents continuous monitoring of the surface water quality in the studied watershed and hinder the feasibility and effectiveness of implementing the HRMA approach.

The severe pollution of the Wadi El Bey watershed, the security concerns that prevent continuous in-situ use of sensors, the high cost of the sensors, their high sensitivity, and the issues with their maintenance and calibration prevent continuous monitoring of the water quality in the studied area and hinder the viability and effectiveness of putting the HRMA approach into practice.

The following additional photos show the extreme pollution situation of rivers in Wadi El Bey studied area:

Figure 10. Photos illustrating the severity of water quality degradation in the Tunisian case study and the urgent need for management intervention.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Sustain-COAST project is a research and innovation project that aims to turn Research and Innovation actions into concrete value and impact for society. Sustain-COAST monitoring task is one of the core activities of the project that aims at improving public, political and social knowledge and action on groundwater quantity and quality.

This deliverable has outlined the results of implementing HRMA in the Greek and Tunisian case studies as two specific demo sites experiencing severe groundwater quality deterioration and continuous decline in groundwater level. Under rapidly changing climatic and anthropogenic pressures, there is a strong need for knowledge-based, participatory decision-making through the development of a new generation of model-based and HRMA monitoring-supported information systems and their structured embedment in management structures. This deliverable is a step towards improving awareness about data sharing and systematic monitoring in typical case studies, as the Greek and Tunisian case studies considered here.